

GC-MS analysis of hexane extract of *Jatropha curcas* L. seed oil

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ABSTRACT

The spectral interpretation here was based on compounds identification. The following fatty acids were identified considering the peaks and library fragments; Oleic acid, Stearic acid, Palmitic acid, Margaric acid, 6-Octadecenoic acid, Elaidic acid, Erucic acid, Methyl ricinoleate, 11-octadecenoic acid, 10-undecenoic acid. The results indicated that the *Jatropha curcas* L seed oil has potential in the production of cosmetics, perfumery and pharmaceuticals.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Jatropha curcas L is a perennial, drought resistant plant which is native to Central America but grows well on tropical and subtropical regions of the world. The oil from the seeds of the plant has been used as an industrial raw material since long time ago. The oil can be used for producing soap, cosmetics and candles [1]. Soxhlet extraction, physicochemical analysis and cold process saponification of Nigerian *Jatropha curcas* L. seed oil was reported [2]. A review Cosmetic potentials of physic nut (*Jatropha curcas* Linn.) seed oil was also reported [3]. *J. curcas* L. has also attracted a great deal of attention worldwide, regarding its potential as a new biodiesel crop [4]. *J. curcas* L. (JCL) is a popular energy crop in tropical countries. The crop has multiple uses including supply of energy. The major source of energy from JCL the seed oil, which can be used in the raw form or as biodiesel [5]. Nutritional and chemical composition of *J. curcas* (L) seed oil from Nigeria was reported [6]. Oil extraction and cosmetic potential or prospects for cosmetic products were reported [7,8]. This work present GC-MS Analysis of Hexane Extract of *J. curcas* L. Seed Oil (Figure 1d) and justify its potential for

cosmetics, perfumery and pharmaceutical preparations.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Seed material

Indigenous *J. Curcas* L. seeds were obtained from *J. curcas* plant in a test plot at Warra town Ngaski local government area of Kebbi State, Nigeria. The plant was identified and authenticated by a Botanist at the Biological Sciences Department, Bayero University, Kano (BUK) Nigeria. Confirmation of taxonomic identity of the plant was achieved by comparison with voucher specimen (voucher No. 110) kept at the Herbarium of the Department of Biological Sciences. The seeds were selected and damaged ones were discarded. The seeds were cleaned, de-shelled and well dried and ground using laboratory plastic pestle and Mortar prior to extraction.

2.2. Oil extraction procedure

The hexane extract was obtained by complete extraction using the Soxhlet extractor (GG-17, SHUNIU). The 50 g of each powdered kernel sample was put into a porous thimble and

placed in a Soxhlet extractor, using 150 cm³ of n-hexane (with boiling point of 40- 60°C) as extracting solvent for 6 hours repeatedly until required quantity was obtained. The oil was obtained after evaporation using Water bath at 70°C to remove the excess solvent from the extracted oil. The oil was then stored in refrigerator for subsequent physicochemical analysis.

2.3 Percentage yield

The oil which was recovered by complete distilling of most of the solvent on a heating mantle was transferred to a beaker. The beaker was then placed over water bath for complete evaporation of solvent for about 2 hours and volume of the oil was recorded and expressed as oil content (%) in line with literature report [9].

2.4. Determination of color

The color of the oil samples was determined by observation using several independent competent individuals. Oil color was correlated using color charts [10].

2.5 Physico-chemical chemical analysis

The Physico-chemical analysis of the seed oil was carried out using the methods and results as previously reported [2].

2.6 GC-MS analysis of the *J. curcas* L. seed oil

The analysis of the fatty acids in the onion seed oil sample was done at National Institute of Chemical Technology (NARICT), Zaria, Nigeria, a Shimadzu QP2010 plus series gas chromatography coupled with Shimadzu QP2010 plus mass spectroscopy detector (GC-MS) system was used. The temperature programmed was set up from 70°C to 280°C. Helium gas was used as carrier gas. The injection volume was 2 µL with injection temperature of 250 °C and a column flow of 1.80 mL/min for the GC. For the mass spectroscopy ACQ mode scanner with scan range of 30-700 amu at the speed of 1478 was used. The mass spectra were compared with the NIST05 mass spectral library [11].

Figure 1. (a) *Jatropha curcas* L. plant; (b) *J. curcas* L. fruits; (c) *J. curcas* L. fresh seeds; (d) Hexane extract of *J. curcas* L. seed oil.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Oleic acid, Stearic acid, Palmitic acid, Margoric acid, 6-Octadecenoic acid, Elaidic acid, Erucic acid, Methyl ricinoleate, 10-undecenoic acid were the major fatty acids found.

Oleic, Palmitic, and Stearic Acids are fatty acids with hydro- carbon chains ranging in length from

12 to 18 carbons with a terminal carboxyl group. These fatty acids are absorbed, digested, and transported in animals and humans. As reported [12], little acute toxicity was observed when Oleic, Palmitic, or Stearic Acid or cosmetic formulations containing these fatty acids were given to rats orally at doses of 15-19 g/kg body weight. Feeding of 15% dietary Oleic Acid to rats in a chronic study resulted in normal growth

and health, but reproductive capacity of female rats was impaired. Results from topical application of Oleic, Palmitic, and Stearic Acid to the skin of mice, rabbits, and guinea pigs produced little or no apparent toxicity. Studies using product formulations containing Oleic and Stearic acids indicate that neither is a sensitizer or photosensitizing agent. Animal studies also indicate that these fatty acids are not eye irritants. Lauric, Stearic, and Oleic Acids were noncarcinogenic in separate animal tests. In primary and cumulative irritation clinical studies, Oleic, and Stearic Acids at high concentrations were nonirritating. Cosmetic product formulations containing Oleic, Palmitic, and Stearic Acids at concentrations ranging up to 13% were not primary or cumulative irritants, nor sensitizers. On the basis of available data from studies using animals and humans, it was concluded [12] that Oleic, Palmitic, and Stearic Acids among others are safe in present practices of use and concentration in cosmetics.

Margaric acid was also detected. Heptadecanoic acid, or margaric acid, is a saturated fatty acid. Its molecular formula is $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{15}\text{COOH}$. It does not occur in any natural animal or vegetable fat at high concentrations. A sample of external carcass fat of sheep has been investigated and it has been found to contain appreciable quantities of margaric acid [13].

6-Octadecenoic acid was also found. It is also known as Petroselinic acid, a fatty acid that occurs naturally in several animal and vegetable fats and oils. In chemical term it is classified as monosaturated omega -12 fatty acid. It can be used in cosmetics.

Elaidic acid is another fatty acid from the fragments. Elaidic acid (a 9-trans isomer of oleic

acid, a monosaturated trans- fatty acid, an unsaturated fatty acid that is the most widely distributed and abundant fatty acid in nature. It is used commercially in the preparation of oleates and lotions, and as a pharmaceutical solvent [14].

The results also indicated the availability of Erucic acid. Erucic acid is a monounsaturated omega-9 fatty acid. It is known as monounsaturated because it has only one double-bonded carbon atom in its fatty acid chain. The term omega-9 refers to a group of fatty acids, including erucic and oleic acid, which have their double carbon bond occurring at the ninth position from the end of their acid chains. This is known as the n-9 position. Products produced using erucic acid include cosmetics [15]. Methyl ricinoleate was also found. Methyl ricinoleate or Ricinoleic acid methyl ester is a naturally occurring 12-hydroxy fatty acid constituting about 90% of the fatty acids in castor oil [16].

A novel constituent, 11-octadecenoic acid, reported for the first time in a seed oil of *Asclepias syriaca* L. (common milkweed) was also found. 11-Octadecenoic acid differs from most natural unsaturated fatty acids in having the double bond at the seventh carbon atom from the methyl end of the chain [17].

Another fatty acid obtained is 10-undecenoic acid (Undecylenic Acid) a monomer derived from ricinoleic acid [18] is an organic unsaturated fatty acid pyrolysis product of ricinoleic acid from castor oil, , it is used in the manufacture of pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and perfumery, including antidandruff shampoos and antimicrobial powders (Santa Cruz Biotech, 2014).

Figure 1. Typical GC-MS total ionic chromatogram (TIC) of hexane extract *Jatropha curcas* L. seed oil.

Hit#3 Entry:22869 Library:NIST05s.LIB

SI:88 Formula:C18H34O2 CAS:112-80-1 MolWeight:282 RetIndex:2175

CompName:Oleic Acid \$9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)- \$\$.delta.(Sup9)-cis-Oleic acid \$cis-.delta.(Sup9)-Octadecenoic acid \$cis-Oleic Acid \$cis-9-Octadec

Hit#3 Entry:22977 Library:NIST05s.LIB

SI:88 Formula:C18H36O2 CAS:57-11-4 MolWeight:284 RetIndex:2167

CompName:Octadecanoic acid \$Stearic acid \$n-Octadecanoic acid \$Himko Industrine R \$Hydrofol Acid 150 \$Hystrene S-97 \$Hystrene T-70 \$Hys

Hit#5 Entry:22219 Library:NIST05s.LIB

SI:91 Formula:C17H34O2 CAS:112-39-0 MolWeight:270 RetIndex:1878

CompName:Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester \$Palmitic acid, methyl ester \$n-Hexadecanoic acid methyl ester \$Metholene 2216 \$Methyl hexadecanoate \$

Hit#4 Entry:22212 Library:NIST05s.LIB

SI:88 Formula:C17H34O2 CAS:506-12-7 MolWeight:270 RetIndex:2067

CompName:Heptadecanoic acid \$n-Heptadecanoic acid \$n-Heptadecoic acid \$n-Heptadecylic acid \$Margarinic acid \$Margarinic acid \$Normal-heptade

Hit# 4 Entry:23567 Library:NIST05s.LIB

SI:88 Formula:C19H36O2 CAS:2777-58-4 MolWeight:296 RetIndex:2085

CompName:6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester, (Z)- \$\$ Methyl cis-6-octadecenoate \$\$ Methyl petroselinate \$\$ Methyl (6Z)-6-octadecenoate # \$\$

Hit# 1 Entry:23570 Library:NIST05s.LIB

SI:93 Formula:C19H36O2 CAS:1937-62-8 MolWeight:296 RetIndex:2085

CompName:9-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester, (E)- \$\$ Elaidic acid, methyl ester \$\$ Methyl elaidate \$\$ Methyl trans-9-octadecenoate \$\$ (E)-9-Octadecenoic aci

Hit# 2 Entry:121691 Library:NIST05.LIB

SI:92 Formula:C22H42O2 CAS:112-86-7 MolWeight:338 RetIndex:2572

CompName:Erucic acid \$\$ 13-Docosenoic acid, (Z)- \$\$ delta.13-cis-Docosenoic acid \$\$ cis-13-Docosenoic acid \$\$ (Z)-13-Docosenoic acid \$\$ Prifrac 2990 \$\$

Hit# 1 Entry:24270 Library:NIST05s.LIB

SI:87 Formula:C19H36O3 CAS:141-24-2 MolWeight:312 RetIndex:2247

CompName:Methyl ricinoleate \$\$ Ricinoleic acid methyl ester \$\$ 9-Octadecenoic acid, 12-hydroxy-, methyl ester, [R-(Z)]- \$\$ Flexicrin P-1 \$\$ Methyl ricinolat

Hit#:2 Entry:98778 Library:NIST05.LIB

SI:86 Formula:C19H36O2 CAS:52380-33-3 MolWeight:296 RetIndex:2085

CompName:11-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester \$\$ Methyl 11-octadecenoate \$\$ Octadec-11-enoic acid, methyl ester \$\$ Methyl (11E)-11-octadecenoate # \$\$

Figure 2. Results from the fatty acid fragments of *Jatropha curcas* L. seed oilTable 1. Major fatty acids derived from hexane extract of *Jatropha curcas* L. seed oil

S/N	Name of fatty acid	MF	MW	RI	SI% to T.C.
1.	Oleic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	282	2175	88
2.	Stearic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284	2167	88
3.	Palmitic acid	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ O ₂	270	1878	91
4.	Margaric acid	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ O ₂	270	2067	88
5.	6-Octadecenoic acid	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₂	296	2085	88
6.	Elaidic acid	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₂	296	2085	93
7.	Erucic acid	C ₂₂ H ₄₂ O ₂	338	2572	92
8.	Methyl ricinoleate	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₃	312	2247	91
9.	11-octadecenoic acid	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₂	296	2085	86
10.	10-undecenoic acid	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ O ₂	184	1461	87

Note: S/N = Serial number, M.F.=Molecular formula, M.W. = Molecular weight, RI= Retention index SI% = Similarity index, T.C. = Target compound.

4. CONCLUSION

From the results of the GC/MS Analysis of *Jatropha Curcas* L. Seed Oil, it can be concluded that the seed oil has potential in the production of cosmetics, perfumery and pharmaceuticals

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

AAW designed the study, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript, managed the analyses of the study and the literature searches. Interpretation and write up of the manuscript were done by authors AAW and AA. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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